

INSTITUTIONAL BASIS OF MANAGEMENT OF BUSINESS AND CRAFTS DEVELOPMENT IN NEIGHBORHOODS IN GREEN ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

In this article has been described the institutional basis of managing the development of entrepreneurship and crafts in neighborhoods.

1. Introduction

As a result of comprehensive measures implemented for the development of national handicrafts, folk art and practical art, and comprehensive support for industry representatives, the number of master craftsmen in our country has increased by 7 times and the number of apprentices by 9 times in the last five years. The number of people employed in the industry reached 230,000.

A national catalog of folk art of craftsmen was created, and 340 masters who won honorary and international exhibitions and competitions were included in this catalog. Also, about 1.5 thousand artisans have been included in the tourism register and are contributing to the development of this industry.

At the same time, it is required to take additional measures to make full use of unused opportunities through neighborhood work, to further expand the system of exchange of experience among craftsmen, and to find new markets for handicraft products.

The most important part of the society in the consistent implementation of the goals and tasks set before us in order to ensure the sustainable development of our country, increase the well-being of our people, and ensure that our citizens are satisfied with their lives and live a dignified life with firm faith in tomorrow. The role and importance of the neighborhood institution is increasing more and more.

2. Analysis and results

The neighborhood is the most important for our people in strengthening the environment of peace and harmony, mutual respect, kindness and harmony in the society, preserving national traditions and values, ensuring the cohesion of families, raising a healthy and mature generation, and solving the daily problems of the population. It is a close social structure.

At the same time, in order to find out the problems of the population and alleviate their burden by going door-to-door of citizens' gatherings, state agencies, including the People's

Reception Rooms of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as the People's Reception Rooms) and the regions with comprehensive social- it is required to strengthen cooperation with economic development sectors (hereinafter referred to as sectors), to improve material and technical support, and to implement specific measures regarding the appropriate evaluation of the work of industry employees.

In order to increase the effectiveness of the role and activity of the neighborhood in the management of society, to introduce modern mechanisms of organizing the work of citizens' meetings, to attract qualified, rich life experience and selfless personnel to the field:

1. A cooperation system was introduced based on the principle of "neighborhood — sector — People's Reception — neighborhood" for working with appeals, identifying and solving population problems, and the following are the main directions of this system.

Also, from January 1, 2020, together with the National Project Management Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the "Neighborhood" electronic database was launched as part of the "Electronic Government" system.

In the next few years, Uzbekistan is also making efforts to further develop handicraft entrepreneurship and increase its importance in the country's economy. We know that for the development and expansion of business entities, an economic and legal base must be created. Currently, such an economic and legal base is being created. In order to ensure the development of this sector, a number of laws are being passed and strategic plans are being developed for their implementation.

The restoration and development of this industry in Uzbekistan, which has ancient roots, has a number of specific signs and characteristics, namely:

- striving to realize one's potential;
- independent and free engagement in creative, interesting work;
- to provide decent living conditions for their loved ones;
- the desire to implement ideas that have a social, economic and cultural effect.

In order to fulfill the above-mentioned wishes, the craftsman must organize his activity process consistently. For this, the craftsman should be based on marketing research, forecasting the development of the market situation when making important decisions. That's when craft entrepreneurship develops, and its place and importance in the economy increases. This can be seen in:

- firstly, craft entrepreneurship creates a competitive environment necessary for the market;
- secondly, it quickly adapts to the changing market demand;
- thirdly, it plays an important role in solving the employment problem;
- fourthly, it helps to quickly fill the gap that arises in the consumer sector;
- fifth, uses raw material resources and waste efficiently.

In addition to the above, handicrafts play an important role in the country's economy and social development. The best part of handicrafts in the neighborhoods is that it is efficient and cost-effective, based on age-old national traditions. [5]

The contribution of craft entrepreneurship in neighborhoods to economic development is as follows:

- craft business is largely adapted to meet local needs;
- offers customized products instead of standard products;

- produces new products in accordance with national traditions and values.

At the current stage of reforms, deepening the liberalization of the economy, expanding the opportunities for earning income of the subjects on the basis of its modernization was defined as the main task. Because market relations are based on economic interests and it is achieved by earning and profiting.

In Uzbekistan, the level, types, and increase in the income of the population is a matter that has a special place in the income policy of the state. The income policy of the state is aimed at creating conditions for the increase of the population's income, social support of the population, protection of the low-income population, mitigating the problem of poverty, and sharply reducing poverty. [1]

An important aspect of crafts in neighborhoods is that there is a unity of kinship and mutual economic life and the common appropriation of results. Such activities are based on meeting the economic, social and spiritual needs of small groups, individuals and families.[2]

Not only the economic aspect, but also the social aspects of handicrafts in the neighborhoods are of particular importance. Crafts embody the social status of people, economic conditions and national traditions formed in society, and ensure their preservation and transmission from generation to generation.[3]

Quantitative features of this profession are that, while the number of people employed in it is a minority, they are mainly family members or close relatives of the family. At the same time, sometimes craftsmen-masters operate using the labor of apprentices. [4]

Based on the economic, social and quantitative characteristics of crafts in the neighborhoods, we would like to emphasize that it is necessary to pay attention to the following directions of its development:

- crafts should be considered as one of the means of initial capital accumulation, and should be able to be a source of livelihood for a wide segment of the population;
- craft production serves to fill the market with products and services, and can enter into competition with large manufacturers in some branches of production;
- the development of crafts should be the main factor in reducing the rate of unemployment;
- crafts develop a person's independent activity, allow him to show his personal characteristics, help him find his place in society and enter into market relations.

As can be seen from the above, craft entrepreneurship can become a real resource of socio-economic and cultural development in our country. It also indicates the strengthening of civil society institutions, the expansion of opportunities for the population to acquire, distribute and use handicraft products, and to improve the individual's self.

3. Conclusion

In our opinion, in order to further develop handicrafts in the neighborhoods and thereby ensure the employment of the population, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- learning and introducing advanced foreign practices in the development of crafts and household activities, i.e. providing home services by phone, advocacy, creating software products;
- to carry out extensive propaganda work among the population about homesteading activities, its advantages, benefits and reliefs given by our government for the development of homesteading, to increase the image of homesteading among the public;

- development of economic mechanisms that will allow artisans and homemakers engaged in informal activities to transfer to formal activities;
- mastering types of craft activities specializing in the production of new goods and services suitable for changing market conditions.

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